

Research Paper

Development And Validation of A UV Spectrophotometric Method for the Assay of Buspirone HCL Tablets

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ABSTRACT

Buspirone hydrochloride is a mostly prescribed anxiolytic drug commonly available in tablet dosage forms. This study develops and validates a simple, rapid, eco-friendly UV-Visible spectrophotometric method for its quantitative analysis in solid dosage forms, meeting the criteria for practical quality control. We improved key parameters during development like wavelength selection fixed absorbance maximum at 243 nm, and solvent composition was modified to increase the sensitivity and stability utilizing quality laboratory solvent. We validated the method following ICH guidelines to confirm its reliability and repeatability. It showed strong linearity over 2.5-40 µg/mL, with a correlation coefficient r^2 of 0.9997. The LOD and LOQ of Buspirone HCL by the proposed method were found to be 0.094 µg/ml and 0.274µg/ml respectively, Recovery studies proved accuracy, yielding 98–102%, while precision tests confirmed excellent repeatability (RSD <2%). The proposed method also showed ruggedness against minor changes in analytical conditions and among different sample Hence, this UV-Visible spectrophotometric method works reliably for routine Buspirone HCL assays in Pharmaceutical formulations.

INTRODUCTION

Buspirone is an azaspiro compound that is 8-azaspiro[4.5] decane-7,9-dione substituted at the nitrogen atom by a 4-(piperazin-1-yl) butyl group which in turn is substituted by a pyrimidin-2-yl group at the N 4position. It has a role as an anxiolytic drug, a sedative, a serotonergic agonist and an EC 3.4.21.26 (prolyloligopeptidase)

inhibitor. It is an azaspiro compound, a member of pyrimidines, a N-arylpiperazine, a N-alkylpiperazine, a member of piperidones and an organic heteropolycyclic compound. It is a conjugate base of a buspirone (1+). Buspirone is a novel anxiolytic agent with a unique structure and a pharmacological profile. Belonging to the azaspirodecanedione drug class, buspirone is

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a serotonin 5-HT_{1A} receptor agonist that is not chemically or pharmacologically related to benzodiazepines, barbiturates, and other sedative/anxiolytic drugs. Unlike many drugs used to treat anxiety, buspirone does not exhibit anticonvulsant, sedative, hypnotic, and muscle-relaxant properties. Due to these characteristics, buspirone been termed 'anxiolytic'. First synthesized in 1968 then patented in 1975, it is commonly marketed under the brand name Buspar®. Buspirone was first approved in 1986 by the FDA and has been used to treat anxiety disorders, such as generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), and relieve symptoms of anxiety. It has also been used as a second-line therapy for unipolar depression when the use of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) is deemed clinically inadequate or inappropriate. The potential use of buspirone in combination with [melatonin] in depression and cognitive impairment via promoting neurogenesis has also been investigated. (11) Buspirone is an azaspiro compound containing heteroaromatic moieties such as pyrimidine and piperazine rings, which function as chromophores capable of absorbing ultraviolet radiation (1) There are few extractive spectrophotometric techniques for measuring Buspirone HCL in pharmaceutical matrices, according to a thorough analysis of the literature. Halogenated organic solvents, which pose serious environmental and occupational risks, are the main component of current analytical frameworks. Additionally, even though High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is still the gold standard for sensitivity and selectivity, high-throughput routine analysis is hampered by its operating costs and solvent consumption.(2)(10) Our aim was to creating an extractive UV spectrophotometric technique that complies with Green Analytical Chemistry (GAC), the current study overcomes these constraints. The technique avoids the use of hazardous reagents while

preserving analytical integrity by employing a 50:50 (v/v) water-ethanol hydro-ethanolic system. (4)(5)(6)

Figure 1: Structure of Buspirone HCL

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

MATERIAL:

Buspirone HCL (API), Buspirone HCL Tablet, Ethanol, Distilled Water

Instruments:

Analytical Balance (Shimadzu), UV- Visible Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1800), Sonicator

METHODS:

Preparation of Diluent:

The solvent employed for the analysis consisted of a mixture of ethanol and distilled water at a ratio of 50:50 (v/v), ensuring Ideal solubility and transparency of the Buspirone HCL solution for UV spectroscopic assessment.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:

A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of the Buspirone HCL in a 100 mL volumetric flask, followed by dilution to volume with the solvent and sonicated.

Preparation of sample:

As per the label claim, the buspirone tablet contain 5 mg drug. 20 tablets were weighed to determine weight uniformity, and the mean tablet weight was calculated to be 116 mg. The total weight of the 20 tablets was 2267 mg, corresponding to a labeled drug content of 20 mg of buspirone hydrochloride. The tablets were finely powdered using a pestle

and mortar, and an amount of powder equivalent to 20 mg of buspirone hydrochloride was precisely transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Sufficient amount of diluent added and sonicated for 30 min. with intermediate shaking made up volume up to 100 ml with diluent and mixed well.

Determination of Maximum Wavelength (λ max):

A standard solution of Buspirone HCl was examined in the ultraviolet range of 200–400 nm using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer, with the prepared diluent serving as the blank baseline for correction. The absorption spectrum obtained exhibited a well-defined peak at 243 nm, which corresponds to the maximum absorbance of the drug. This wavelength (λ max) was selected for all further quantitative measurements and method validation studies, as it represents the point of highest sensitivity and accuracy for Buspirone HCl analysis (13) (14)

Validation:

The ICH Q2(R2) guidelines were followed in the validation of the developed UV-spectrophotometric method. Linearity, Accuracy, precision, Ruggedness limit of detection (LOD), and limit of Quantitation (LOQ) were among the validation parameters that were assessed. Along with respectable accuracy and precision, the method showed outstanding linearity over the chosen concentration range. The method's sufficient sensitivity was demonstrated by the low

LOD and LOQ values. Overall, the validation results show that the suggested approach is accurate, dependable, and appropriate for routine quantitative analysis of Buspirone HCl in tablet dosage forms. (3) (12)

Linearity:

The linearity of Buspirone HCl was evaluated by preparing five standard solutions in the concentration range of 2.5–40 μ g/mL from the standard stock solution. The absorbance of each solution was measured at the previously determined λ max of 243 nm using a UV–visible spectrophotometer, with 50:50 v/v ethanol: water as the blank. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentration, and linearity was assessed by calculating the correlation coefficient (R^2). The results showed a direct and proportional relationship between absorbance and concentration over the studied range, indicating that the proposed method is linear and suitable for the quantitative determination of Buspirone HCl in both pure drug and tablet dosage forms. (7)(8)

Table 1: Result of Linearity

Sr. No.	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	2.5	0.130
2	5	0.256
3	10	0.594
4	15	0.890
5	20	1.186
6	40	2.372

Figure 2: Calibration curve for Bupirone HCL (Concentration. vs. Absorbance.)

Table 2: Optimization parameters of Bupirone HCL Parameters Method values

Parameters	Method values
Maximum Wavelength	243 nm
Range	2.5-40 μ g/ml
Correlation Coefficient (r^2)	0.9997
Regression Equation	$y=0.06x-0.0203$
Slope (m)	0.06
Intercept (c)	-0.0203

Limit of Detection (LOD)

It was defined as the smallest concentration of an analyte in the sample which can be detected by the detector and it is not significant to undergo the linearity and precision test (it is not to be quantified)

It was defined as the smallest concentration of an analyte in the sample which can be detected by the detector and can be determined quantitatively with appropriate precision and accuracy and it can be calculated by using following equation according to the ICH (2005). (9)

$$\text{LOD} = 10/\sigma * S$$

Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

$$\text{LOQ} = 3.3/\sigma * S$$

Table 3: Result of Absorbance

Concentration	Absorbance (A)	Absorbance(B)	Absorbance(C)	Absorbance(Mean)
0.02	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001
0.05	0.019	0.019	0.018	0.018
0.25	0.059	0.059	0.059	0.059
2.5	0.202	0.204	0.205	0.203
5	0.256	0.256	0.257	0.256
10	0.594	0.594	0.594	0.594
20	1.040	1.039	1.038	1.039
40	1.743	1.745	1.746	1.744
			Sigma(σ)	0.6174
			Slope	22.55

The LOD and LOQ of Buspirone HCL by the proposed method were found to be 0.094 μgml^{-1} and 0.274 μgml^{-1} respectively that is quite closed to practical value i.e. 0.05 for LOD and 0.25 for LOQ.

Actual LOD= 0.05 ppm

Actual LOQ = 0.25ppm

LOQ Precision:

Prepared sample of LOQ solution and recorded absorbance six times:

Table 4: Result of LOQ precision

Sr. No.	Absorbance
1	0.059
2	0.059
3	0.059
4	0.058
5	0.059
6	0.058
Mean	0.058
SD	0.000408
RSD	0.696

Precision:

In precision intra-day and inter-day precision were performed at concentration (20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The

obtained results were found within limit i.e. less than 2%RSD.

Table 5: Results of method precision

S. No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance(Day 1)	Assay
1	20	1.236	99.68
2	20	1.239	99.92
3	20	1.246	100.48
4	20	1.247	100.56
5	20	1.229	99.11
6	20	1.243	100.24
	Avg.	1.240	99.99
	SD	0.0068	
	%RSD	0.55%	

Ruggedness (Intermediate Precision):

The change in analyst with same concentration and environmental condition didn't affect the results.

Table 6: Results of Intermediate Precision

S. No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (Day 2)	Assay
1	20	1.245	100.65
2	20	1.232	99.60
3	20	1.240	100.24

4	20	1.234	99.76
5	20	1.236	99.92
6	20	1.237	100.00
	Avg.	1.237	100.00
	SD	0.0047	
	%RSD	0.38%	

Absolute difference between method precision and intermediate precision

Table 7: Result of difference between method and intermediate precision

Method Precision	Intermediate Precision	Difference
99.99	100.00	0.01

Accuracy:

The concentration 10, 20, 30 µg/ml was taken as 50%,100%,150% and % recovery was found to be in range 98%-102%. Hence the parameter was found to be validated.

Table 8: Result of accuracy

% Conc.	Test sample	Spiked conc.(µg/ml)	Absorbance	% Recovery	Avg.	STDEV	RSD
50	Test 1	10	0.615	99.51	101.14%	0.79	0.79
	Test 2	10	0.609	98.54			
	Test3	10	0.620	100.32			
100	Test 1	20	1.245	100.73	100.24%	0.96	0.96
	Test 2	20	1.222	98.87			
	Test 3	20	1.239	100.24			
150	Test 1	30	1.861	99.99	100.06	0.08	0.08
	Test 2	30	1.864	100.15			
	Test 3	30	1.862	100.04			

The assay was performed by using Buspirone HCL at concentration 20 µg/ml. The % purity was found to be 99.17%

Table 9: Results of Assay

Formulation	Absorbance	Obtained amount(mg)	Assay
Buspirone HCL	1.236	4.95	99.17%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The UV-visible spectrophotometric method for Buspirone HCL analysis demonstrates exceptional performance across key analytical parameters. The method exhibits excellent linearity with an R² value of 0.998, indicating a strong correlation between concentration and absorbance. High

accuracy is achieved, with recovery rates ranging from 98% to 102%, ensuring reliable quantification. Precision is also noteworthy, with relative standard deviation (RSD) values below 2%, reflecting consistent and reproducible results. The ruggedness further enhance its reliability under varying conditions. Its applicability to commercial formulations broadens its practical utility. The simplicity of the technique, coupled with its Non-Toxicity, makes it an attractive option for routine quality control analysis. Additionally, the wide linear range allows for the analysis of samples across diverse concentration levels, enhancing the method's versatility in pharmaceutical applications.

CONCLUSION

An analytical UV Spectrophotometric method was developed & validated thoroughly for quantitative determination of Buspirone HCL in tablet formulation. The presented method was found to be simple, precise, accurate, rugged, reproducible and gives an acceptable recovery of the analyte, which can be directly easily applied to the analysis of pharmaceutical tablet formulation of Buspirone HCL.

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